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DAUGHTERS OF INVENTION: USING DRAMA TO ENGAGE CHILDREN WITH ENGINEERING

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ABSTRACT

Daughters of Invention is a UK funded drama and engineering project which is developing primary school children's understanding of engineering and STEM subjects. The project targets girls and children from Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic (BAME) backgrounds in areas of high deprivation in Birmingham, UK. The project consists of four interactive and immersive drama and engineering workshops for 240 children aged 9-10, from four inner city primary schools. The workshops are led by experienced drama practitioners from The Play House (UK) and a team of eight engineering students and staff from the University of Birmingham. The project develops the students' outreach and public engagement skills and encourages them to develop their own projects in the future. The workshops use drama and storytelling to provide a dynamic, human story for the children to engage with and give them an impetus to solve the engineering challenges presented to them.

Daughters of Invention was originally created through a Royal Academy of Engineering Ingenious award (UK) and delivered to 240 children in four primary schools in Birmingham (UK) in 2019. The feedback from the first phase was extremely positive and our initial preliminary evaluations demonstrate that the project had a

significant impact. The second phase of the project is currently underway (2020) and at the end of this phase there will be a set of evaluation activities including questionnaires/focus groups/interviews, to determine the effectiveness of using drama and storytelling to engage children with engineering.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Daughters of Invention is a **drama and engineering** project that aims to develop primary school children's understanding of engineering and STEM subjects, raise aspirations and widen their participation in higher education. It also aims to increase engineering students' confidence and skills in outreach and public engagement. The project is delivered by the School of Engineering at the University of Birmingham and The Play House, a theatre in education company with a unique participatory approach to working in schools that uses drama to engage children in a range of subjects and issues.

The project targets girls and children from Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic (BAME) backgrounds in areas of high deprivation in Birmingham. The project consists of a series of four interactive and immersive drama and engineering workshops. It is delivered to 240 children from 8 classes in Year 5 from 4 inner city primary schools. The workshops are led by experienced drama practitioners from The Play House and a team of eight PhD and MEng Biomedical Engineering students from the partnering higher education institution, the University of Birmingham's Mechanical Engineering Department.

Daughters of Invention was originally created through a Royal Academy of Engineering Ingenious award (Ing 718\12\20, 2018) and was delivered to 240 children in four primary schools in Birmingham in 2019. The feedback from the children, teachers and engineers from the first phase was extremely positive and our evaluations demonstrate the project had a significant impact on those involved.

Therefore, a second phase of the project was developed, funded by the the Millennium Point Charitable Trust (STEM Small Grant, 2019) and completed in 2020. This reached a new audience of children and teachers, working with a new cohort of student engineers from Univeristy of Birmingham. We offered 2 student engineers from the 2019 project an opportunity to mentor the new cohort and work with the university to research the impact and potential of the model.

1.2 Literature

The benefits of the use of drama to engage primary school students with science and engineering is widely discussed in the literature. Smith and Herring [1] explains that drama is a powerful tool which enables students to connect learning with content. They

draw from their experience and identify that drama enables students to learn through immersing themselves in the experience and empowering them with new knowledge through actively engaging with the activity. This analogy was identified in our workshops, where students were active participants in the workshops.

Of interest to our study is also Abed's [2] study, which investigated the effect of using drama in science teaching with school children. The focus of their study was on students' understanding of scientific concepts and their attitudes towards learning science. They concluded from their study that there is educational benefit in using drama in teaching science, by again describing drama as a powerful tool with the potential to change the mindset of students who previously in their study viewed the traditional science class as rigid and boring to a post study view of one that is lively and entertaining through the introduction of drama.

Other examples can be drawn from Najami et al. [3] who concluded from their study that embedding drama into chemistry classes contributes to students' curiosity in studying chemistry and positively impacts their grades. While, Boujaoude et al.'s [4] study focused on the effect of using drama as a method to support science students' learning strategy. When compared with their control group, their results concluded that the students' in the drama group were able to demonstrate more informed views on aspects of science. The outcomes of these studies are consistent with our preliminary observations from the first study.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Primary School student workshop framework

A number of fictional characters interacted with the children and the engineers acted as themselves, to provide a dynamic, problem solving, human story for the children to engage with. The narrative focused on a biomedical emergency, where the children had to design, build and test a medical device for fixing a broken bone. The drama brought to life the real story of Mrs Sarah Guppy, an 18th Century engineer from Birmingham. By contrasting the challenges she faced with the experiences of the current engineers we will demonstrate that engineering is a career open to anyone. Daughters of Invention culminated in a celebration event at the University of Birmingham campus, during British Science Week, for the children to share their engineering creations. The creative and engineering team worked with one class at a time, giving a highly participatory and bespoke experience based on the children's needs.

At the start of the project training was provided for the student engineers on outreach and public engagement to prepare them for the project and signpost them to support available at the University of Birmingham. During rehearsals, engineers learnt storytelling techniques and gained an insight into a different way of communicating

their research and journey's as engineers with the public. At the end of the project, there is an evaluation workshop. The framework of the project was as follows:

Intervention 1 – the children are introduced to a female professional footballer who is due to play in the world cup but has broken her leg. The engineers and the characters in the drama enlist them to design a device to fix the bone. The children meet Sarah Guppy, a real life 18th Century engineer, who explains the challenges faced as a woman, and the children act out scenes from her life.

Intervention 2 – the children design, build and test their devices to fix the broken bone. The engineers and the characters teach the children about forces, teamwork, the engineering design process, prototypes and the importance of learning from your failures and trying again. To help the children understand how engineering benefits society Sarah Guppy gets the children to perform scenes showing the impact their device has on the footballer's life.

Intervention 3 – the engineers ask the children to help them with a presentation at the University next week about their journey as engineers. The engineers use storytelling to tell the children what/who inspired them to be engineers as children and their current research. Sarah and the other characters then help the children to improvise scenes from the engineer's life. The children also produce a poster showing their devices.

Intervention 4 – The children visit the Collaborative Teaching Laboratories at University where they present their devices and perform scenes from the engineer's lives.

2.2 Target groups

The schools targeted in Birmingham (UK) had high numbers of pupils from Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic communities, and will be from socio-economic categories NS-SEC 15-8 [5] and have over 50% of their pupils receiving Pupil Premium funding. Teachers value the work from this project as being able to engage with children who have limited English and encourage more complex vocabulary, particularly effective for children who are functionally bilingual. This project introduced the children to engineering concepts and terminology in a supportive environment where they were safe to explore new ideas and make mistakes.

When recruiting the engineering students we identified female engineers and students from BAME backgrounds (our two priorities), to showcase the diversity in engineering and promote the inclusivity agenda. PhD students who took part in phase one shared their experiences and we used the promotional film to inspire potential project candidates. These testimonials delivered a powerful message and resonated with other likeminded students. In addition, personnel from the main project team are from BAME backgrounds and underrepresented groups in engineering, which will strengthen our take home message.

¹ National Statistics Socio-economic Classification

2.3 Workshop Evaluation methodology

The evaluation activities described in this section were approved by the University of Birmingham (UK) Ethics Research Committee.

The evaluation consists of:

- 1) a pre and post project evaluation questionnaire to be completed by:
 - Students from the University of Birmingham
 - Children completing the workshops (Under 18 population)
- 2) Separate focus group sessions post project for each of the following groups:
 - Children completing the workshops (Under 18 population)
 - Drama practitioners from The Play House
- 3) Separate individual interviews for:
 - Teachers from the primary schools participating in the workshop

3 RESULTS

The analysis of the evaluation data focuses predominantly on the post project feedback, since this is more readily available in the current COVID-19 emergency measures. The following areas can be reported.

3.1 Analysis of evaluation data: Post project evaluation questionnaire (university students)

The 8 university students were asked to reflect on their experience and rate on the following:

- How would you rate your level of confidence when talking to the general public about your work (from a scale of very confident to not at all confident)?

8 students responded and the results are shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1. Confidence level post project

The 8 students were asked to reflect on the following:
- Which of the following benefits did you gain from this project?

8 students responded and the results are shown in Fig.2.

Fig. 2. Benefits of participating in the project

Following these, within the free-text sections students were asked to reflect via a series of questions and a summary of the responses is included below.

- *Was the project enjoyable? Please share why or why not?*

“I really enjoyed it! Never thought of combining engineering and drama together to teach kids about engineering”

“it involved many of the things I like – working with kids, acting, public speaking (and talking about myself). It felt like the kids were really engaged, retained info well and enjoyed.”

- *What were the two main learning outcomes for you?*

- Be confident about myself in terms of public speaking

- To improve my communication skills with the children

- To value my own story and be confident in sharing it

- Combination of group activities with theatre is an effective method of outreach

- I should aim for simplicity and study my audience very well

- Being able to demonstrate to school children that Engineering and other STEM subjects are those they can feel empowered to undertake

- great reminder that teachers have questions about other careers too, and it helped me think about how you can educate two different groups of people at the same time

- I learnt how to adapt my speech/presentation skills for different groups and to recognise which things they might and might not engage well with

- How to present engineering ideas in a way children can understand

- *In what ways has being part of the project changed your attitude to public engagement?*

- I would like to continue outreach work when I join the engineering industry, and help students in school or university to explore the industry.

- I got to see it in a new light because I wouldn't immediately think to explain engineering to children in this way – involving figures from the past, mixed with the present day, but it worked really well and I would be a lot more confident to do something like that again.

- *In what way has being part of the project changed your attitude to working with young people?*

- I love inspiring young people and from previous experience, it's amazing what students can achieve with just a little inspiration and push.

- I wouldn't say it's changed my attitude much as it's something I've done one and off for a while, but it did reignite my desire to continue working with children and reminded me why I love it.

For the final two questions, the students were asked to reflect on the two following questions:

- *In what ways has being part of the project developed your skills?*
- *In what ways has being part of the project enhanced your career?*

There was much similarity between the key descriptors reported by the 8 students, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Skills and career descriptors reported

3.2 Analysis of evaluation data: Post project focus group sessions (school children)

The school children were asked to reflect on their experience and asked the following questions.

- *What skills do you think you need to have to be an engineer?* The key words used are summarised in Fig.3.
- *What did you enjoy doing the most as a part of the project?* The key words used are summarised in Fig.4.

Fig. 3. Skills needed to be an engineer

Fig. 4. Enjoyed the most

Following these, the school children were asked to reflect on the project via a series of questions and a summary of the responses is included below.

- *How is problem solving good for doing engineering?* Students identified: Not all the answers come to you, sometimes you have to dig deeper. It is not just there for you to pick out; to try different ways to get it right; need to figure out how to do it carefully; solve problems quick if you good at it and rapidly help people sometimes things may not go the way you expected and have to pick yourself up again and try again; if you make prototype and afterwards there is something wrong with it, then when you actually do the thing you can figure out what is wrong with it.
- *How is being creative good for doing engineering?* Students explained: To figure out different ways of doing things to it and add more flare and more things to improve it; It will look very nice and you will have a better design.
- *What did you enjoy the least?* Students identified: Team work challenges; time restrictions
- *What could have made this project better?* Students identified: Focus on different subjects and outdoor activities and more drama activities

3.3 Analysis of evaluation data: Post project individual interviews (primary schools teachers)

The school teachers were asked to reflect on their experience and asked the following questions. To date one teacher has responded and full responses are quoted below.

- *What impact has this project had on the children in your class?*

“This has a profound impact on the children in both our classes, they have grown in both confidence and understanding of STEM and in particular Bio- Mechanics. During the project some children were interviewed for the UNICEF Rights Respecting Schools Silver Award and spoke at length about the project to the assessors. The assessors said that they had a tone of assurance and knowledge as they explained how they were helping a footballer who had been injured. Most children would not have known anything about bio - mechanics and certainly not the parallels between the mechanics of bridge building and that of current engineering. But now they do and so will their families, so the project has a far reaching impact.”

- *Has this project increased the children's experience of STEM?*

“Yes of course. To spend focused time with people who are highly knowledgeable on a STEM project set within a creative frame so that the children can fully access it has given them the chance to have a deeper learning experience. I think that because it was a STEAM as well as STEM project it was most effective. The children responded to the needs of the athlete and loved 'meeting' Sarah Guppy too. This way of working

included a range of different learning styles which meant all children were able to experience STEM in a way that they would remember in the future.”

- *How will it support your teaching?*

“It will be something that has shown both teachers children responding to science through a dramatic frame and how that can be effective. The children will take this experience into Year 5 and 6 and further into secondary school. I did a drama session on the project afterwards and the children were able to explain the mechanics, the modern day dilemma and the story of Sarah Guppy.”

- *In what ways has this project raised the children’s aspirations?*

“Most of our children have had quite a limited experience of things outside their realm so we as a school make it our aim to raise aspirations and give them those additional opportunities which might inspire them to become a scientist or architect or performer. This project has opened their eyes to the learning opportunities for those who are interested in engineering; it will have explained what engineering actually is and it has also shown them that you can be a female engineer. It was a shame they didn't get to the university but they do go in year 5 and 6 and so that understanding that they don't have to go away from home to aspire is also important.”

- *Is there anything you would change or do differently?*

“It worked really well as it was. I would, having worked with them between sessions, perhaps set up some kind of recap for either the teachers to do or at the start of the session before you develop the story/ knowledge. I found that some children were a little confused and needed a bit of unpicking before they could fully participate in the drama work (whereas some got it all) - a week can be quite a long time when you are 8 years old, particularly if your first language isn't English and you are taking in many many things during that week.

It wouldn't need to be long (and you may already do it) but a 5 minute recap - including some of the scientific knowledge - would bring everyone on board and ensure anyone who missed a session is clear. I know teachers could do this but if you do it there is a clarity and purpose that is slightly different.”

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Both the quantitative and free text responses collected through the evaluation activities demonstrated that the project objectives were met. The children focus group responses demonstrated that they have grasped the engineering principles through engaging with the project. The rest of the project team involved also responded positively and expressed overwhelmingly the benefits and developmental opportunities as a result of their participation.

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